

ISic1424

I.Sicily inscription 1424

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

lex sacra

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara

Hyblaia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI301103

1. Πασαράτ-
2. ο *h*ãδε· *h*ός κ-
3. ā τῶ ἀρχῶ μ [ἐ̄]
4. ἀρούε[ι] {²⁷μάρούε[ι]}²⁷ ὀγδ-
5. ὅαν . . .
- 6.

Edition: PHI330075

1. Πασαράτ-
2. ο̄ *h*άδε □ *h*ός κ-
3. α (τὰ) τὸ ἄρχο̄μ-
4. α ὀ̄ θύε, ὀγδ-
5. ὅαν ἀποτ ε [ι]-
6. σάτο̄ □ αἰ̄ δὲ [— —]
7. [—]N[— — —]A [— — —]
8. [— — —]AΘ[— — —]δε-
9. κα λιτρὰς □ ἄ-
10. ποτεισάτο̄.

11.

Edition: PHI330147

1. Πασαράτ-
2. ο̄ háδε □ hòς κ-
3. à (τ) τῶ ἀρχομ-
4. áō θύε̄, ὄγδ-
5. ὅαν ἀποτε[ι]-
6. σάτο̄ □ αἰ δέ [τ]-
7. [ί]ν[εσθ]α [ι λῆ]
8. [άν]ὰ η[εκαί]δε-
9. κα ²⁶έκκαίδεκα²⁶ λίτρας □ á-
10. ποτεισάτο̄.

11.

12. . . . αἰ δέ [κ]-
13. [α λῆ πρ]ᾶ [ξαι]
14. [άν]ὰ . . .

15.

Edition: PHI331812

1. πᾶσι □ ἀρὰ □ τῶ □ [θ]-
2. [ε]ῶ □ háδε □ hòς κ-
3. à (τ) τῶ ἀρχομ-
4. áō θύε □ ὄγδ-
5. ὅαν ἀποτει-
6. σάτο □ αἰ δέ [— —]
- 7.

Edition: PHI333363

1. Πασά[ρ]ατο [ς]
2. [h]ο háδεφος κ-
3. α (τὰ) τῶ ἀρχῶ M[α]-
4. [λ(?)]άρου ²⁶Μαλάκου²⁶ ε' ὄγδ-
5. ὅαν ἀποτε[ι]-
6. σάτο̄ □ αἰ δέ [λ]-
7. [ἔι(?)] τῶ ἐνιαυτ]-
8. [ῶ χαλκῶ(?)] ξέ-
9. κα λίτρας □ á-
10. ποτεισάτο̄ □

11.

Edition: PHI333755

1. Πασάδατο [ς]
2. [h]ο háδε□hos κ-
3. α (τὰ) τῶ ἀρχῶ M[α]-
4. [λ]άρου ²⁶Μαλάκου²⁶ ε' ὄγδ-

5. óav . . .

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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PHI 330075

PHI 330147

PHI 331812

PHI 333363

PHI 333755

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